

Deliverable D9.1 First report on external GIDE network engagement

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AWS	Amazon Web Services
BIA	BioImage Archive
CPG	Cell Painting Gallery
ELMI	European Light Microscopy Initiative
EMIM	European Molecular Imaging Meeting
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESMI	European Society for Molecular Imaging
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FBbi	Biological Imaging Methods Ontology
GBI	Global BioImaging
GIDE	Global Image Data Ecosystem
GloBIAS	Global BioImage Analysts Society
HMC	Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration
IDR	Image Data Resource
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
LABI	Latin America BioImaging
OME	Open Microscopy Environment
OMERO	Open Microscopy Environment Remote Objects
PID	Persistent Identifiers
QUAREP-LiMi	Quality Assessment and Reproducibility for Instruments and Images in Light Microscopy
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDM	Research Data Management

REMBI	Recommended Metadata for Biological Images
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
SSBD	A platform for Systems Science of Biological Dynamics
TiM	Trends in Microscopy
vEM	volume Electron Microscopy
XNAT	eXtensible Neuroimaging Archive Toolkit

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Executive Summary

This report outlines the activities carried out in foundingGIDE to drive engagement with biological and preclinical imaging communities through targeted outreach activities and technical coordination events. In addition to various imaging communities, relevant groups of data holders, data managers and metadata experts, as well as specialised research infrastructures that could support relevant topics around foundingGIDE were engaged. These activities support the development of an interoperable and collaborative network, fostering collaboration, exchange of expertise and alignment of standards and recommendations across biological and preclinical imaging domains. Community engagement is a key component, and an ongoing effort that will continue throughout the duration of the project.

1. Introduction

FoundingGIDE aims to establish the foundation for a Global Image Data Ecosystem (GIDE) by reaching consensus and coordinating with the global bioimage community, on a set of ontologies and harmonised metadata schema. FoundingGIDE is connecting European research infrastructures and image data resource owners with their counterparts in Australia and Japan, thereby establishing the groundwork for seamless image data sharing across continents.

foundingGIDE partners and collaborators have actively engaged with imaging communities driving bioimage standards to promote the project objectives and to connect to understand their unique challenges. These interactions and activities aim to raise awareness about the technical developments proposed by foundingGIDE and drive adoption of the project recommendations.

2. Engagement with technical communities, training and outreach

Outreach and engagement activities with the global imaging community are essential to ensure that the solutions recommended within foundingGIDE are aligned with the practices and challenges faced by researchers, data producers and data providers. Community engagement with diverse stakeholders enables the project to remain responsive to emerging challenges, capture a wide range of perspectives, and create an interoperable and inclusive GIDE.

We define a technical community as a group of experts, whether affiliated to an organisation or a grassroots effort, that works towards addressing challenges in image data generation, or general data research data management (RDM) practices that can be relevant for making image data into a findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) global resource. The group activities may range from developing tools, file formats, metadata standards, all the way to simple exchange of experience from a thematic group on their specific imaging challenges. Knowledge of such relevant efforts is key to help the foundingGIDE project understand the challenges and potential solutions towards a truly global and FAIR image data ecosystem.

Figure 1. Type of the outreach and dissemination activities from January 2024 to June 2025

Dissemination activities play a key role in amplifying the reach and impact of foundingGIDE. Through a combination of digital communications, conference participation, publications and meetings, the project ensures that its goals, progress, and outcomes are visible to a broad and diverse audience, including researchers, infrastructure providers, policy makers, and other global initiatives. These dissemination efforts not only raise awareness but also invite collaboration and alignment with

complementary activities in the imaging and data communities. The following graph showcases the various channels and formats through which foundingGIDE disseminates its work, highlighting both the diversity and strategic targeting of its communication efforts.

The diverse locations of our dissemination activities underscore the robust global outreach strategy of the project, demonstrating a commitment to engaging with a wide spectrum of international stakeholders and ensuring broad awareness of our initiatives. This global engagement is crucial for fostering the collaborative spirit necessary to build an effective global data ecosystem.

Country of the dissemination activity

Figure 2. Country of the outreach and dissemination activities from January 2024 to June 2025

2.1. Dedicated engagement with technical communities

The dedicated engagement with technical communities focuses on establishing and maintaining bidirectional interactions with expert imaging communities and related initiatives. The goal is to understand the evolving needs of these communities, disseminate project outcomes, and foster alignment and uptake of foundingGIDE developments. Liaisons from the project partners actively engage in community meetings and working groups, acting as bridges between foundingGIDE and the respective communities.

Engagement with Euro-BiolImaging Nodes and expert groups

FoundingGIDE has actively engaged with the Euro-BiolImaging Nodes through participation in the annual Euro-BiolImaging All Hands Nodes meetings and a dedicated two-hour session at the [Euro-BiolImaging's Image Data Community Days](#) event. These interactions have been crucial for disseminating the project's progress, understanding community needs, and fostering potential collaborations.

foundingGIDE was presented to the broader Euro-Biolmaging community at two consecutive annual All Hands Nodes meetings ([2024](#), [2025](#)). These presentations provided an overview of the project's objectives, timeline, and, notably, the ongoing efforts in metadata harmonisation for biological and preclinical image data. At the 2025 meeting, a dedicated panel discussion explored data management practices. A key point of interest throughout these sessions was the community's questions on the progress of metadata harmonisation and the recommendations for ontology use.

Building on these initial interactions, foundingGIDE held a dedicated two-hour session during the Euro-Biolmaging Image Data Community Days, a virtual event held in [April 2025](#). This session offered a more in-depth look into specific technical aspects of the project, including the selection of ontologies, the recommendation of a set of ontologies for preclinical imaging, the harmonisation of metadata schemata, and the use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) within the bioimaging context.

These engagements led to insightful discussions with the Euro-Biolmaging community. A primary concern raised by the community members revolved around the challenge of developing standards that can comprehensively cover the diverse modalities and intricate details inherent in biological imaging data. The presentations and discussions generated significant interest within the Euro-Biolmaging Node community and allowed the project partners to understand the challenges and concerns from one of their key stakeholder groups.

Engagement with QUAREP-LiMi

FoundingGIDE is actively engaged with Quality Assessment and Reproducibility for Instruments and Images in Light Microscopy ([QUAREP-LiMi](#)), a grassroots community that focuses on light microscopy image and image data quality management, specifically through its [Metadata Working Group](#). Project representatives participate in ongoing discussions to harmonise metadata standards in light microscopy in the monthly meetings. The interaction ensures that foundingGIDE tools and outputs remain relevant to the quality control and reproducibility requirements of this key community. FoundingGIDE also benefits from these discussions by integrating current best practices into its own ontology and metadata recommendations outputs. Representatives of the group were also involved in the 2024 technical coordination event.

Engagement with GloBIAS

In the Global BioImage Analysts Society ([GloBIAS](#)), foundingGIDE contributes through both the Communications Working Group and Training and Activities Working Group. These collaborations are instrumental in raising awareness of foundingGIDE's goals and progress within the global image analysts' community, which are primary and secondary users of image data, and developers and maintainers of analysis methods. Our involvement supports the promotion of open science values and facilitates the dissemination of GIDE outputs such as guidelines, ontologies, and training resources through GloBIAS's networks.

Engagement with EDAM Bioimaging

FoundingGIDE is working closely with the [EDAM Bioimaging](#) team to support the use and development of EDAM Bioimaging ontology. This collaboration was featured prominently in our [2024 technical event](#) ([Technical event report](#)) and is being extended through bilateral meetings to explore long-term synergy. These efforts aim to ensure interoperability of bioimaging metadata across platforms, not just limited to imaging, in line with FAIR principles. EDAM Bioimaging is emerging as a critical tool for standardising terms and identifiers, and foundingGIDE's input helps align this ontology with the needs of imaging researchers.

Engagement with Cell Painting Gallery

FoundingGIDE has initiated discussions with the Cell Painting Gallery ([CPG](#)) initiative to explore collaborative pathways. The CPG is a publicly accessible collection of datasets created using the Cell Painting assay (Bray *et al.* 2016), curated by the [Imaging Platform at the Broad Institute of MIT and Harvard](#). This open resource for image-based profiling has already one dataset in OME-Zarr format, currently browsable via Image Data Resource ([IDR](#)). Our collaboration has highlighted the potential of CPG to adopt foundingGIDE recommendations. These early conversations lay the groundwork for deeper technical and strategic collaboration in future project phases.

Engagement with Research Data Alliance

FoundingGIDE is collaborating with the [Life Science Data Infrastructures Interest Group](#) of Research Data Alliance ([RDA](#)) on a session focused on multimodal data integration in the life sciences for [International Data Week Conference 2025](#). This session will showcase efforts from ELIXIR, EMBL-EBI, Euro-BioImaging, and Instruct-ERIC, and will explore emerging standards and practices for integrating and sharing multimodal data, such as imaging, structural, and genomic data, within the framework of a federated Life Science Research pilot node in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). FoundingGIDE will contribute with perspectives from the ongoing work of laying the foundations of a GIDE, and highlight challenges and opportunities related to interoperability, standards harmonisation, and ontology alignment.

This collaboration will provide a valuable opportunity to position foundingGIDE as a contributor to international discussions on data federation and integration. The project's involvement will help raise awareness of specific imaging challenges and solutions within the global RDA community as well as future alignment with relevant RDA working and interest groups.

Engagement with National Imaging Infrastructures

One of the objectives of foundingGIDE is to provide guidance towards an ecosystem where new image repository solutions, like those supported at a national level, can connect to the global harmonisation efforts in the project. This involves engagement with representatives from national repositories that are currently under development to make sure their solutions are interoperable. During the project, we have engaged with [Czech BioImaging](#) and [Netherlands BioImaging](#) initiatives from the Euro-Bioimaging Nodes community, to promote harmonised developments; an engagement that continues. This indicates a strong potential for the uptake and impact of foundingGIDE's recommendations.

Engagement with volume Electron Microscopy community

FoundingGIDE engaged with the volume Electron Microscopy (vEM) community particularly during the foundingGIDE Community Event 2024, which was designed to bring together diverse imaging communities. The vEM community was actively represented during this event, both through a dedicated speaker presentation and through participation in the workshops and discussions. This interaction provided valuable insights into the specific challenges and needs of vEM in the context of large-scale data management and metadata harmonisation. The contributions of the vEM representatives helped ensure that the perspectives and requirements of this community are considered in the development of foundingGIDE recommendations.

Engagement with ELIXIR

The project is engaging with relevant European Research Infrastructures to provide guidelines that promote interoperability of image data. ELIXIR, the European infrastructure for access to biomolecular data, provides various data services, including interoperability services, such as EDAM

ontologies, and solutions, such as RO-Crate, that help foundingGIDE build cross-domain solutions. foundingGIDE aims and outputs have been presented at bilateral collaborative meetings with ELIXIR Hub in February 2024 and March 2025, and at a larger ELIXIR All Hands Meeting in June 2025. Additionally some of the project partners are involved in the RO-Crate community to adopt the latest developments and engage as a user of RO-Crate. These interactions support our interoperability towards biomolecular and omics data, keeping us up to date with the latest developments in RDM solutions.

Engagement with EOSC

The EOSC is a key place for the foundingGIDE project to interact with the European policy landscape and understand requirements for integrating into an envisioned web of FAIR data and services. Through Euro-Biolmaging's membership of the EOSC-Association and participation in EOSC task forces, the project has been able to provide input on the multiannual roadmap that informs the future Horizon Europe calls. The project was also presented at the EOSC Symposium in 2024, as it aims to bring the aspects of global coordination and technical solutions to the European landscape, through the partners' participation in the EOSC federation.

Engagement with Global Biolmaging

foundingGIDE has actively engaged with the Global Biolmaging (GBI) network and broader imaging and data communities to foster collaboration and promote the global adoption of the project outcomes. One of the key strategies has been coordinating the first foundingGIDE Community Event 2024 back-to-back with GBI Exchange of Experience 2024, ensuring that stakeholders from both initiatives can participate, exchange insights, and align efforts. These back-to-back events served as a crucial platform for engaging local and regional communities in exchanging knowledge on imaging data interoperability.

Through Global Biolmaging, foundingGIDE deepened its international engagement by participating in [a week-long Study Visit](#) with imaging scientists from the Latin America Biolmaging (LABI) network and contributing to the India Biolmaging (IBI) community during the [IBI meeting](#) (see Table 1), further expanding its collaborative reach across diverse geographic regions.

FoundingGIDE partners are active participants in the [Image Data Management](#) and [Biomedical Imaging Data](#) working groups of Global Biolmaging. They are leading the working groups and regularly participating in discussions, contributing with their expertise and integrating insights back into foundingGIDE outputs. The Image Data Management working group focuses on challenges and best practices for managing imaging data, while the Biomedical Imaging Data working group focuses on enhancing the visibility and integration of biomedical imaging within the global network

Further strengthening this engagement, the Global Biolmaging [Biomedical Imaging Data Workshop](#) featured the foundingGIDE project. This event provided a dedicated space to discuss imaging data challenges, opportunities for global interoperability, and how the foundingGIDE outcomes can benefit the broader community.

Future engagements

During the project, foundingGIDE will continue to identify and reach out to additional expert groups that align with its goals. Liaisons will be nominated to attend community events, provide support, and establish mutual connections between foundingGIDE activities and those of the broader imaging community. Representatives from these communities are also invited to participate in technical and community events organised by foundingGIDE, further fostering cross-promotion of efforts and

initiatives. These exchanges are essential to refining project outputs and building a sustainable and truly global ecosystem for interoperable image data.

2.2. Community meetings, training and outreach on technical themes

FoundingGIDE partners and collaborators have actively engaged with the bioimaging community through contributions to numerous workshops, conferences, and training events. At these gatherings, the partners and collaborators disseminated information on the project's ongoing developments via presentations and poster sessions.

The following table offers a detailed overview of foundingGIDE's active participation in key community events, highlighting the commitment to engaging with and informing the broader bioimaging community about the project progress and objectives.

Table 1. Highlighted community events with foundingGIDE's active participation

Date	Location	Summary
May 2024	Dundee, UK	The 2024 Open Microscopy Environment (OME) Community Meeting highlighted how institutions are involved in the OME ecosystem. Discussions concerning the development and adoption of common metadata standards and file formats emerged as one of the main topics of the meeting. The foundingGIDE image data repositories partners (Systems Science of Biological Dynamics Database (SSBD), BioImage Archive (BIA) and IDR highlighted their active efforts within the project to harmonised the metadata model of these three image data repositories. https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/ome-community-meeting-2024/
May 2024	Heidelberg, Germany	The 2024 Helmholtz Imaging Conference brought together specialists in imaging data, with topics ranging from foundation models for single-cell images in hematology to x-ray tomography of historical artifacts and automated pipelines for metadata annotation. Discussions with Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC) experts focused on exploring synergies and strengthening the potential for future partnerships. This meeting provided a valuable opportunity to disseminate our efforts and connect directly with the community to strengthen collaboration and exchange on metadata standards. https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/foundinggide-helmholtz-imaging-conference-2024/
June 2024	Liverpool, UK	The 2024 European Light Microscopy Initiative (ELMI) annual meeting was attended by more than 600 researchers and service providers across Europe and the world interested in light microscopy technology development. The foundingGIDE project was presented to this expert audience as part of a talk during the core facilities' day, at the poster session and to further engage with the community project partners, hosted

Date	Location	Summary
		the “Global BioImaging: Accelerating Collaboration and Innovation through Data Dialogue” Community Room. https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/elmi-2024/
July 2024	Brisbane, Australia	The Australian National Imaging Facility Annual Scientific Meeting 2024 brought together the Australian imaging community. It featured advanced imaging techniques, transformative applications spanning from preclinical to human research, imaging data management and analysis techniques, and interactive sessions designed to foster collaboration. The local project partners highlighted foundingGIDE efforts around developing a preclinical imaging metadata model recommendation and a set of tools for collecting and storing metadata on the XNAT platform. https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/foundinggide-at-the-australian-national-imaging-facility-annual-scientific-meeting-2024/
September 2024	Heidelberg, Germany	The Latin American Imaging Scientists’ Study Visit event welcomed several research facility managers and imaging scientists from across Latin America, providing a unique opportunity for international collaboration. The presentation of foundingGIDE during the study visit provided valuable insights and led to discussions about the data management challenges faced by our Latin American counterparts, strengthening the potential for future partnerships. https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/foundinggide-x-imaging-scientists-from-latin-america/
December 2024	Pune, India	India BioImaging Community Meeting 2024 brought together facility managers, imaging scientists, and decision-makers from across India to strengthen the country’s bioimaging infrastructure and foster collaboration. Discussions centered on how global initiatives like foundingGIDE can support the Indian BioImaging community objectives, particularly in addressing challenges around data sharing, harmonisation, and infrastructure development. https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/foundinggide-at-india-bioimaging-community-meeting/
March 2025	Bilbao, Spain	The European Molecular Imaging Meeting (EMIM), organised annually by the European Society for Molecular Imaging (ESMI), is a dynamic and collaborative event that brings together over 1,000 international attendees from various imaging science fields. The foundingGIDE partners highlighted foundingGIDE efforts around developing a preclinical imaging metadata model recommendation and a set of tools for collecting and storing metadata on the XNAT platform. https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/foundinggide-at-european-molecular-imaging-meeting/
March 2025	Münsingen, Germany	Throughout Trends in Microscopy (TiM) 2025, the recurring emphasis on metadata standards, image data interoperability,

Date	Location	Summary
		<p>and global sharing highlighted the increasing importance of these challenges for the imaging community. FoundingGIDE is actively integrating these insights into our ongoing work. This meeting provided a valuable opportunity to disseminate our efforts and connect directly with the community through workshops attendance and during the poster session.</p> <p>https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/data-management-and-interoperability-at-trends-in-microscopy-2025/</p>
March 2025	Heidelberg, Germany	<p>The annual Euro-Biolmaging All Hands Nodes Meeting 2025 brought together scientists from Euro-Biolmaging Nodes to connect, foster interdisciplinary collaboration, and discuss key topics related to Euro-Biolmaging operations and imaging technology developments. FoundingGIDE hosted a dedicated session where partners presented ongoing efforts to harmonise metadata schemas and identify a recommended set of ontologies for the imaging community. The session concluded with a panel discussion that sparked valuable insights and feedback from participants.</p> <p>https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/foundinggide-session-at-euro-bioimaging-all-hands-nodes-meeting-2025/</p>
April 2025	Virtual	<p>Euro-Biolmaging Image Data Community Days 2025 is a five-day long virtual event bringing together the imaging community, including Euro-Biolmaging Node staff, researchers and other experts from across the globe to explore and discuss the latest advancements in the field of image data. FoundingGIDE had a two-hour dedicated session offering a more in-depth look at specific technical aspects of the project, including the selection of ontologies, the recommendation of a set of ontologies for preclinical imaging, the harmonisation of the metadata schema, and the use of PIDs within the bioimaging context.</p> <p>https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/foundinggide-at-euro-bioimaging-image-data-community-days/</p>
April 2025	Virtual	<p>The Biomedical Imaging Data Workshop organized by Global Biolmaging brought together researchers working with biomedical imaging data. The discussion focused on imaging data repositories, global interoperability challenges, and infrastructure solutions for biomedical imaging data featuring panelists from foundingGIDE that shared their expertise and experiences.</p> <p>https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/foundinggide-at-global-bioimaging-biomedical-workshop/</p>
May 2025	Woods Hole, US	<p>OME Community meeting 2025 brought together international experts in biological imaging, data management and open science to explore the evolving OME ecosystem, challenges in data sharing, and collaborative strategies for building a more interoperable and FAIR future in bioimaging. FoundingGIDE was highlighted by the project partners.</p>

Date	Location	Summary
		https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/foundinggide-at-the-2025-ome-community-meeting/
June 2025	Heidelberg, Germany	The 2025 European Light Microscopy Initiative annual meeting was attended by more than 500 researchers and service providers across Europe and the world interested in light microscopy technology development. FoundingGIDE presented a poster showcasing its efforts to improve data interoperability and reusability in biological and preclinical imaging. The poster highlighted ongoing work on harmonising metadata standards, developing common ontologies, and engaging with imaging communities to align practices and infrastructures. https://founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu/foundinggide-at-elm-i-2025/

3. First technical coordination event

The first foundingGIDE technical event “foundingGIDE BioImage Hackathon” was an in-person developer event hosted at the RIKEN institute in Kobe, Japan from 4th to 8th of November 2024. The event brought together developers, ontologists, researchers, and image data experts from around the globe. This event represents a milestone (MS2) of the project.

47
participants

9
countries

5
days-long

3
workshops

from foundingGIDE insert
Biolmage Hackathon

WHEN
4th - 8th of November 2024

WHERE
Kobe, Japan

Figure 3. First technical event promotional material and overview agenda ([technical event webpage](#), [detailed agenda](#))

The technical coordination event combined two tracks: a hackathon and in parallel two workshops focused on data management and image analysis. The hackathon served as an essential continuation of the discussions and connections made during the foundingGIDE Community Event 2024. The

practical, hands-on nature of the hackathon enabled participants to collaboratively develop solutions for these challenges while the workshops allowed participants to learn new skills around data management and image analysis.

The hackathon track of the technical event focused on foundingGIDE's core goals to enhance interoperability in biological imaging leading to the development of tools and valuable discussions around ontologies, while the two workshops focused on practical implementation of data management tools and image analysis.

3.1. First technical coordination event – hackathon track

The foundingGIDE technical event brought together international experts to address key challenges in bioimaging data interoperability and standardisation. Multiple focused working groups were established, each tackling a specific theme relevant to ontology integration, metadata representation, and FAIR data packaging. This report summarises the main outcomes of the five working groups.

Figure 4. Technical event opening by Shuichi Onami and participants attending the session

Table 2. Summary of the working groups outcomes of the Technical event 2024

Working group	Outcome
Ontology deep dive: FBbi & EDAM	<p>Project contributors: Hiroshi Masuya, Koji Kyoda, Adriaan Ludl, Caterina Strambio De Castilla, Aastha Mathur, François Sherwood</p> <p>Goals: Compare two imaging method ontologies: FBbi and EDAM BioImaging, for use in metadata standards to represent the 'type of imaging that was used to capture a specific image'</p> <p>Achievements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FBbi has better structure for this specific problem, despite less coverage of imaging methods. • Generation and manual review of a mapping for all relevant terms in FBbi to terms already covered in EDAM BioImaging. <p>https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1e257s8gmFy7wa5-6dxLyOMVZEgHfr24-8cJl3hftVWE/edit?gid=1497866547#gid=1497866547</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Created a tool to map classes from one taxonomy to another based off the manual mapping: https://github.com/foundingGIDE/hackathon_2024_metadata_ontologies/tree/main/fbbi_edam_mapper <p>Next Steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reach out to FBbi owners (as the common communication channels were inactive) to see if we can get proposals into FBbi as new development will be required for new imaging methods.
OMERO-RDF	<p>Project contributors: Josh Moore, Maria Mirza</p> <p>Goals: Expand the plugin for exporting RDF data from OMERO (omero-rdf) to allow the generation of JSON-LD and more specifically RO-Crate Object</p> <p>Achievements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working version (PR#25) of JSON-LD and RO-Crate output (Subsequently released as 0.5.0) Tested the RDF generation against the IDR which is used during the schema.org review. Trained new OMERO-RDF developers <p>Next Steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the following, de.NBI hackathon (Kassel, Dec 9-13), the work will continue to refactor the JSON-LD context used by omero-rdf. Establish a working group to continue the development of the JSON-LD context and publish the context for others to consume.
schema.org review	<p>Project contributors: Josh Moore, Matthew Hartley</p> <p>Goals: Evaluate schema.org fields for their utility as GIDE, specifically BIA & IDR, terms in the JSON-LD context.</p> <p>Achievements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Due to time constraints, the focus was on all properties of type Person (and to a lesser extent, Organisation). All fields of those types were evaluated against S-BIAD667 as an example. Many fields can effectively be mapped to schema.org fields, increasing the richness of the fields. Detailed results are on the “schema.org” tab of the FoundingGIDE Ontologies-REMBI spreadsheet <p>Next Steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate all other fields, possibly on a base-type basis. Make use of identified fields in the JSON-LD context.

<p>Ontologies for Imaging+</p>	<p>Project contributors: Aybuke Kupcu Yoldas, Koji Kyoda, Eusike Dohi, Alexandra Zakieva, Ken Ho</p> <p>Goals: Compare different ontologies for chemical compounds (PubChem and CHEBI) and genes (NCBI gene and Ensembl) and see if they can be mapped to each other. These ontologies were chosen as they're used by SSBD and IDR: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1QeVuzfcMt92eb4ARVji2T2XNd mjK-291/edit?gid=2130561032#gid=2130561032</p> <p>Achievements: There is no easy mapping as all four ontologies checked are very extensive and they all are very valuable. Decision was to support all and map to each other where possible. https://imagesc.zulipchat.com/#narrow/channel/466189-Zzz.3A-.5B2024-11.5D-FoundingGIDE-Bioimage-Hackathon/topic/Ontologies.20for.20Imaging.2B/with/481025900</p>
<p>REMBI in RO-Crate</p>	<p>Project contributors: Aybuke Kupcu Yoldas, Koji Kyoda</p> <p>Goals: Add more REMBI terms in RO-Crate based on the mapping of SSBD and IDR fields to REMBI https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1BfACtjqpFH6OHhG97Tpd6PMqJU16Ap6r/edit?usp=sharing&oid=116889655909957582028&rtpof=true&sd=true</p> <p>Achievements: A small example RO-Crate JSON producing code that includes a compound and gene example using schema.org and REMBI mapping https://github.com/foundingGIDE/zarr-crate</p>

These collaborative activities during the hackathon demonstrate foundingGIDE engagement with key challenges in bioimaging data interoperability. The working groups addressed goals such as ontology alignment, metadata enrichment, and standardised research output packaging laying important groundwork for standardised community practices.

The five-day technical coordination event discussions advanced foundingGIDE's ongoing efforts to identify and recommend a set of ontologies for the bioimaging community as well as harmonising the metadata schemas. These outcomes and discussions provided a foundation for several foundingGIDE deliverables strengthening the project's impact and progress towards its goals.

3.2. First technical coordination event – workshop track

As part of the foundingGIDE Technical Event, two in-depth, hands-on workshops were organised to provide participants with practical training on key tools supporting bioimaging data management and analysis. These workshops not only strengthened technical knowledge within the community but also fostered dialogue around best practices, tool integration, and workflow optimisation.

The first workshop focused on [OMERO](#), a widely used open-source platform for managing, visualising, and analysing biological imaging data. It was divided into three parts: OMERO installation

and configuration, OMERO imaging workflows, and advanced analysis with OMERO. Led by members of the OME team, including Petr Walczysko and Jean-Marie Burel, the workshop offered participants an in-depth, hands-on experience. Attendees learned how to install and configure their own OMERO servers, gaining practical knowledge of this powerful open-source platform for managing biological imaging data. The sessions fostered productive discussions on deployment strategies, troubleshooting common issues, and optimising OMERO for large-scale image data management. By the end of the workshop, participants left equipped with actionable skills and a clearer understanding of how to integrate OMERO into their institutional workflows.

Figure 5. Jean-Marie Burel and Petr Walczysko from the OME leading the OMERO workshop. Right image: Dominik Kutra leading the ilastik workshop.

The second workshop centered on [ilastik](#), a machine learning–based image analysis tool. This one-day, hands-on session was led by Dominik Kutra and introduced participants to ilastik’s capabilities in automated pixel and object level segmentation, classification, and tracking. Through guided exercises and real-world examples, attendees learned how to use ilastik to streamline complex segmentation tasks, an essential component of high-throughput image analysis. The workshop provided participants with both theoretical insight and practical skills to apply ilastik within their own research workflows, especially in the context of large-scale and heterogeneous bioimaging datasets.

3.3. Key Outcomes and technical developments of the first technical coordination event

The first foundingGIDE technical event core challenges focused on developing practical solutions to improve interoperability of bioimaging data. This technical coordination event contributed to incremental progress in several areas relevant to metadata standardisation and interoperability in bioimaging.

The hackathon sessions enabled participants to explore ontology alignment, develop initial tools and mappings, and identify key areas for further work. The accompanying workshops provided hands-on exposure to commonly used tools such as OMERO and ilastik, helping to reinforce practical skills across the community. While many discussions remain ongoing and several outcomes are still in early stages, the event helped clarify technical priorities and established a foundation for continued collaborative development.

Figure 6: Left image: State-of-the-art droid “Mahoro”. Right image: visit at RIKEN’s Fugaku Supercomputer

Beyond the productive working sessions, participants had the opportunity to experience cutting edge technology by visiting RIKEN’s Fugaku Supercomputer, one of the fastest computational resources in the world, which drives advancements in imaging science and data analysis. Participants also had the chance to see a state-of-the-art droid, “Mahoro”, used for automation of biological workflows.

4. Assessment of external outreach and stakeholder engagement

4.1. Key indicators and metrics

Table 3. Key Performance Indicators for the 18 months of the project

Category	Related KPIs	Estimated measure	M18 status
Community outreach	Number of external community events attended	At least 5	29
	Number of non-imaging communities engaged	At least 3	9
Training/Workshops	Number of training/workshops organised/supported	At least 2	5
GIDE technical events	Number of events	At least 2	1
First GIDE Technical event in Kobe, Japan	Number of participants per event	At least 50	47
	Number of technical communities represented per event	At least 5	8
	Number of image data resources represented per event	At least 5	6

While we have met most of our KPIs and exceeded some, there is a small subset of KPIs that fell slightly short in the first reporting period. This insight gives us an opportunity to have a more targeted and focused approach for the last year of the project runtime.

5. Contribution to GIDE sustainability strategy

The sustainability of foundingGIDE is central to ensuring the long-term impact of the project. Achieving this sustainability means not only developing technical solutions, but also establishing partnerships, building an engaged community, and defining pathways for adoption of the project outputs that will allow foundingGIDE to continue to evolve and provide value beyond the duration of the project to the imaging community.

Currently, our sustainability efforts focus on laying the groundwork for the technical, organisational, and community structures that will support foundingGIDE beyond the project's completion. A key aspect of this is engaging with stakeholders who can contribute to and maintain foundingGIDE's outputs over time, as well as preparing for integration with existing national and international initiatives and infrastructures.

Several activities undertaken so far have contributed to the sustainability of the project. One major step has been the engagement with Euro-BioImaging and its member states. foundingGIDE was presented to the Euro-BioImaging Board in May 2024, and a further update was provided in May 2025. These presentations ensure that European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) members are kept informed about foundingGIDE's progress and are prepared to explore opportunities for their national image data infrastructures to contribute to and benefit from foundingGIDE. This engagement with Euro-BioImaging represents a significant opportunity to align foundingGIDE with large-scale European infrastructures and support its integration into long-term strategies at the national and European level. Additionally, the project is kept well up to date with the very active and latest developments in the EOSC and vice versa to make sure that the global image data recommendations and solutions from foundingGIDE can be incorporated in the EOSC in future.

The project has also focused on fostering a strong network of community partners, including imaging infrastructures, data initiatives, and scientific communities. These partnerships are essential to GIDE's sustainability, as they provide expertise, feedback, and avenues for adoption and further development. In addition, foundingGIDE has begun to establish links with international efforts such as Research Data Alliance (RDA) Interest Groups and Working Groups, image.sc communities, and the Global BioImaging Working Group on image data management. These connections help ensure that GIDE aligns with global best practices and can be integrated into a wider ecosystem of imaging data initiatives.

The project is currently developing a clear strategy to guide foundingGIDE's recommendation adoption by infrastructures, research communities, and policy makers as well as establishing discussion groups for disseminating recommendations, tools, and standards. These venues will enable the community to engage with foundingGIDE's outputs, provide input, and support the uptake of its outputs. In parallel. This strategy includes identifying key stakeholders, ensuring alignment with existing initiatives, and discussing outputs with specific technical communities.

All of these efforts contribute to the project's formal sustainability plan, which will define concrete actions, responsibilities, and timelines for ensuring that foundingGIDE remains relevant and useful beyond the lifespan of foundingGIDE. In the second half of the project, these activities will be further strengthened. foundingGIDE will work to formalise sustainability pathways, solidify partnerships, and finalise a sustainability plan that can serve as a guiding document for the long-term future of GIDE. Through these efforts, foundingGIDE will be well positioned to provide lasting value to the imaging community, enable global image data sharing, and support the development of a GIDE.

1. Bray MA, Singh S, Han H, Davis CT, Borgeson B, Hartland C, Kost-Alimova M, Gustafsdottir SM, Gibson CC, Carpenter AE. Cell Painting, a high-content image-based assay for morphological profiling using multiplexed fluorescent dyes. *Nat Protoc.* 2016 Sep;11(9):1757-74. doi: 10.1038/nprot.2016.105. Epub 2016 Aug 25. PMID: 27560178; PMCID: PMC5223290.